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2 Insights into the degradation of microplastics by Fenton 3 oxidation: From surface modification to mineralization

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12 Graphical abstract

13

14 Abstract

15 This work aims at evaluating the fate of microplastics (MPs) along Fenton oxidation. For such
16 goal, realistic MPs (150-250 μm) of five representative polymer types (PET, PE, PVC, PP and EPS)
17 were obtained from commercial plastic products by cryogenic milling. Experiments (7.5 h) were
18 performed under relatively severe operating conditions: $T=80\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; $\text{pH}_0=3$; $[\text{H}_2\text{O}_2]_0=1000\text{ mgL}^{-1}$ (15
19 doses, 1 every 0.5 h); $[\text{Fe}^{3+}]_0=10\text{ mgL}^{-1}$ (5 doses, 1 every 1.5 h). Slight MPs weight losses ($\sim 10\%$)
20 were achieved after Fenton oxidation regardless the MP nature. Nevertheless, oxidation yield clearly
21 increased with decreasing the particle size given their higher exposed surface area (up to 20% weight
22 loss with 20-50 μm EPS MPs). Clearly, MPs suffered important changes in their surface due to the
23 introduction of oxygenated groups, which made them more acidic and hydrophilic. Furthermore,
24 MPs progressively reduced their size. In fact, they can be completely oxidized to CO_2 , as
25 demonstrated in the oxidation of PS nanoplastics (140 nm), where 70% mineralization was
26 achieved. The nature of the plastic particles had a relevant impact on its overall oxidation, being
27 more prone to be oxidized those polymers which contain aromatic rings in their structures (EPS and
28 PET) compared to those formed by alkane chains (PE, PP and PVC). In the latter, the presence of
29 substituents also reduced their oxidation potential. Remarkably, possible leachates released along
30 reaction were more quickly oxidized than the MPs/NPs, so it can be assumed that these dissolved
31 compounds would be completely removed once the solid particles are eliminated. Notably, the
32 leachates obtained upon MPs oxidation were more biodegradable than the released from the fresh
33 solids. All this knowledge is crucial for the understanding of MPs oxidation by the Fenton process
34 and opens the door for the design and optimization of this technology either for water treatment or
35 for analytical purposes (MPs isolation).

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43 **1. Introduction**

44 Due to their outstanding properties, *i.e.* high chemical and biological resistance, easy moulding and low
45 cost, plastics have become an indispensable material for the industry and modern society. Their annual
46 worldwide production has increased exponentially since the production of the first synthetic polymers in
47 1950, and it is expected to double in the next 20 years (MacArthur et al. (2016)). In 2020, almost 370
48 million tonnes of plastic materials are currently produced worldwide (Plastics Europe (2021)).

49 Despite its benefits to the economy and daily life are undeniable, the generation and mismanagement
50 of plastic waste represents a critical environmental challenge. The so-called microplastics (MPs) and
51 nanoplastics (NPs), plastic debris smaller than 5 mm and 1 μm , respectively (Yang et al. (2021)), are the
52 most widespread plastic residues in the environment. MPs and NPs have been detected in almost all
53 ecosystems, whether in continental and oceanic waters, sediments, soils or even bottled water (Rezania et
54 al. (2018); Cox et al. (2019)). Once in the environment, these plastic debris are ingested by a wide range
55 of organisms, especially the aquatic ones, throughout the different trophic levels, resulting in their
56 introduction into the food chain and the final consumption of MPs and NPs by humans (Enfrin et al.
57 (2020)). Although their effects on human health are not yet well understood, they represent a health risk
58 not only due to their accumulation throughout the body, but also due to their capacity to adsorb other
59 persistent pollutants such as pesticides, heavy metals or pharmaceuticals given their high exposed surface
60 areas (Munoz et al. (2021); Wu et al. (2016)).

61 In the last few years, the focus has been placed on the possible role of wastewater treatment plants
62 (WWTPs) in the emission of MPs into the environment. Although WWTPs can usually remove up to 95%
63 of the MPs from water, total removal is hardly found (Sol et al. (2020)), so that WWTPs represent one of
64 the dominant sources of MPs into natural waters (Li et al. (2018)). For instance, it has been revealed that
65 13 billion MPs are released from WWTPs per day in the United States (Mason et al. (2016)), while in
66 Europe, one of the largest WWTPs in Italy, capable of treating water for 1.2 million equivalent population,
67 releases about 160 million MPs per day (Magni et al. (2019)).

68 Advanced oxidation processes (AOPs) have emerged as promising wastewater treatment technologies
69 for the removal of a wide range of pollutants of emerging concern such as pharmaceuticals, personal care
70 products or pesticides (Magni et al. (2019); Ma et al. (2019); Bhat and Gogate (2021); Serrano et al.
71 (2020)). However, their application for the removal of MPs and NPs has been scarcely investigated. The
72 few publications found in the literature are mainly related to the application of photocatalysis
73 (Ebrahimbabaie et al. (2022); Nabi et al. (2021)). In these studies, generally focused on the design of new
74 photodegradable polymeric materials, slight weight losses and subtle surface modifications of MPs have
75 been reported. Recently, Ariza-Tarazona et al. (2020) proposed a photocatalytic process to remove MPs
76 from water, achieving a weight loss close to 72% for high density polyethylene (HDPE) working at acidic
77 pH and 0 °C but requiring a high catalyst concentration (4 g L⁻¹) and long reaction time (50 hours) under
78 visible light.

79 Fenton oxidation is a particularly attractive AOP due to its high cost-effectiveness ratio. So far, this
80 process has been mainly investigated as a pre-treatment method to isolate MPs from different kinds of
81 waters for analytical purposes (Tagg et al. (2016); Hurley et al. (2018)). In a recent article (Liu et al.
82 (2019)), Fenton oxidation has been employed as an accelerated ageing method for two of the most
83 widespread MPs in watercourses: polystyrene (PS) and polyethylene (PE). Subtle modifications in MPs
84 have been reported during this treatment, such as small weight losses or reduction of mean particle size,
85 but a big knowledge gap seems to linger on the actual changes and degradation that MPs/NPs may undergo
86 upon Fenton oxidation. It is crucial to analyse all the modifications these persistent particles can suffer
87 along the oxidation process considering their morphology, particle size, hydrophilicity/hydrophobicity
88 and acid/base properties until they are completely oxidized to CO₂.

89 This work aims to address this challenging issue by deeply evaluating the fate of MPs along Fenton
90 oxidation. To enhance the extension of the oxidation process, the study was carried out under relatively
91 severe operating conditions (80 °C) given the high persistence of plastics. The role of the MPs nature was
92 investigated by using polyethylene terephthalate (PET), polyethylene (PE), polyvinyl chloride (PVC),

93 polypropylene (PP) and expanded polystyrene (EPS) as target pollutants. All of them were obtained from
94 conventional commercial plastic products by cryogenic milling. The impact of the MPs size was
95 afterwards investigated with EPS particles in the range of <50 to 500 μm . Apart from considering weight
96 losses along the oxidation reaction, MPs were fully characterized to evaluate any significant change on
97 their surface as well as on their size and morphology. Once confirmed that the oxidation of MPs
98 progressively reduced their size and increased their hydrophilicity, the treatment of PS NPs was also
99 investigated to evaluate if the solid particles could be finally mineralized. In the same line, the oxidation
100 of a common plasticizer (diethyl phthalate) as representative leachate compound from MPs/NPs, was also
101 investigated. Finally, the biodegradability of the dissolved compounds leached along MPs oxidation
102 process was also analyzed.

103 **2. Materials and methods**

104 *2.1. Materials and chemicals*

105 Nitric acid (65%) (CAS No.: 7697-37-2), hydrogen peroxide solution (30% wt.) (CAS No.: 7722-84-
106 1) and diethyl phthalate (99,5%) (CAS No.: 84-66-2) were supplied by Sigma-Aldrich. Iron (III) nitrate
107 nonahydrate (98%) (CAS No.: 7782-61-8) was provided by Panreac. All these compounds were used as
108 received without further purification. Deionized water was used to perform all the experiments.

109 Commercial plastic products (disposable water bottles, micropipette tips, containers, food trays and
110 pipelines) of different polymer classes (*i.e.* PET, PE, PVC, PP and EPS) were used to obtain the MPs
111 tested in this work (**Table 1**). A commercial NP sample of monodisperse PS (PS-R-KM248) was
112 purchased from microParticles GmbH to further analyse the effect of the particle size on the Fenton
113 process in the nano size range.

114 *2.2. Microplastics obtention and characterization*

115 MPs were obtained by cutting up the above-mentioned plastic products with stainless-steel scissors.
116 The resulting particles were further grinded using a cryogenic mill (CryoMill, Retsch). The milling cycles

117 had a duration of 2 min at a frequency of 30 Hz. Between them, an intermediate cooling time of 1 min at
118 5 Hz was applied. The number of cycles was varied depending on the type of plastic grinded. EPS and PP
119 required 2 and 5 milling cycles, respectively, while PET, PE and PVC required 3 milling cycles. The
120 resulting particles were further sieved to obtain MPs of a standard size range of 150 – 250 μm . To evaluate
121 the effect of MP size on the oxidation yield, EPS was grinded to obtain different size ranges (<50, 50 –
122 100, 100 – 150, 150 – 250 and 250 – 500 μm).

123 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and light microscopic images of the MPs were obtained using
124 a JEOL JSM 6335F and an Eclipse Ci-S/Ci-L (Nikon) microscopes, respectively. Transmission electron
125 microscopy (TEM) images of the NPs were obtained using a JEOL JEM 2100 microscope. Particle size
126 distribution of MPs was also measured by laser diffraction particle-size analysis using the Mastersizer
127 3000 (Malvern) equipment. Prior analysis, samples were suspended in a 5% wt. ethylene-glycol aqueous
128 solution. Elemental analyses (CHNS) were performed in a CHNS-932 elemental analyser (LECO
129 Corporation). Water contact angle measurements were carried out in the sessile mode at room temperature
130 (23 °C) using a Dataphysics OCA 15 system. MPs were placed onto a glass sample holder. The sample
131 was manually pressed using a spatula to reach a flat surface, where a drop of water (10 μL) was finally
132 deposited. The determination of the $\text{pH}_{\text{slurry}}$ of MPs was performed placing 0.2 g of the solid in 10 mL
133 deionized water at different initial pH values ($\text{pH}_0 = 4$, $\text{pH}_0 = 6$, $\text{pH}_0 = 8$). The suspensions were kept in
134 a continuously stirred bottle at room temperature until pH of the slurry was stable (at least, 24 h). Specific
135 surface area of MPs was measured from nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms at -196 °C using a
136 Micromeritics Tristar 3020 apparatus. Nevertheless, negligible area values were obtained (<1 m^2 g^{-1}) in
137 all cases mainly due to the non-porous character of these solids.

138 To further evaluate the surface chemistry of the plastic particles, Fourier transform infrared
139 spectroscopy (FTIR) spectra of both fresh and oxidized MPs were recorded using a FTIR Bruker IFS66v
140 spectrometer. Analyses were carried out by the attenuated total reflectance (ATR) method using a
141 diamond crystal. The carbonyl index (CI) of the materials was estimated following the procedure

142 described elsewhere (Miranda et al. (2021)). Briefly, CI was calculated as the ratio of the carbonyl peak
143 (1850-1650 cm⁻¹) relative to a reference peak following *Eq. 1*:

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$$145 \quad CI = \frac{A_{\text{Carbonyl group}}}{A_{\text{Reference peak}}} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

146 where $A_{\text{Carbonyl group}}$ is the maximum absorbance height of the carbonyl group; $A_{\text{Reference peak}}$ is the
147 maximum absorbance height of the reference peak for each MP.

148 After testing different peaks as reference, those that did not present any significant difference along
149 the Fenton process were selected (1017, 722, 612, 1376, 1493 cm⁻¹ for PET, PE, PVC, PP, EPS,
150 respectively).

151 *2.3. Fenton oxidation of micro- and nanoplastics*

152 Oxidation experiments (7.5 hours) of MPs and NPs were performed at 80°C and acidic pH (pH₀ = 3)
153 in a glass batch reactor (75 mL) under constant stirring (200 rpm). These relatively severe operating
154 conditions were selected after conducting preliminary experiments under ambient conditions where no
155 significant changes were found in the MPs along the oxidation process (data not shown). In the
156 experiments devoted to the oxidation of MPs, the initial MP mass was set at 100 mg, while the initial
157 concentrations of Fe³⁺ and H₂O₂ were established at 10 mg L⁻¹ and 1000 mg L⁻¹, respectively. On the
158 other hand, in the oxidation of NPs, the initial concentration of the plastic particles was set at 20 mg L⁻¹
159 (1.5 mg in 75 mL), while the initial concentrations of Fe³⁺ and H₂O₂ were established at 10 mg L⁻¹ and
160 130 mg L⁻¹, respectively. To enhance the oxidation yield, additional doses of Fe³⁺ (1 mL, 750 mg L⁻¹)
161 were added to the reactor every 1.5 h. In the case of H₂O₂, additional doses (1 mL, 75 g L⁻¹ for MPs
162 oxidation; 1 mL, 9.75 g L⁻¹ for NPs oxidation) were added to the reactor every 0.5 h (once complete
163 consumption of H₂O₂ was reached). A final experiment was carried out to evaluate the degradation of
164 leachates with diethyl-phthalate (DEP) as target pollutant under similar operating conditions ([DEP]₀ = 5

165 mg L⁻¹, [Fe³⁺]₀ = 10 mg L⁻¹, [H₂O₂]₀ = 20.65 mg L⁻¹, 80 °C, pH₀ = 3). Iron was fed as Fe³⁺ instead of Fe²⁺
166 leading to a Fenton-like process of similar characteristics as the conventional one (Pignatello et al.
167 (2006)). Blank experiments carried out at the same operating conditions but in the absence of Fe³⁺ and
168 H₂O₂ allowed to discard any influence of the temperature and acidity on the changes suffered by the MPs
169 along the oxidation process. Likewise, experiments carried out with H₂O₂ but in the absence of catalyst
170 led to negligible changes in the solids, allowing to confirm that Fenton oxidation was the responsible for
171 the changes observed in the oxidation of MPs/NPs in this work.

172 The MPs degradation yield achieved upon Fenton experiments was determined by measuring the loss
173 of weight. For such goal, MPs residues after the oxidation experiments were collected by filtration through
174 a pre-weighed 0.45 µm PTFE filter, then air dried (60 °C) and weighed as the solid product. MPs were
175 not washed before the analyses except for optical microscopic analyses where a subtle acid washing
176 (HNO₃, 0.1M) of the oxidized MPs was performed to remove iron residues from the surface of the plastic
177 particles to better appreciate any morphological change. To follow the oxidation yield along the
178 experiment carried out with PS NPs, total organic carbon (TOC) was measured. It must be noted that the
179 suspension of PS NPs in water was fairly stable, so TOC measurements offered a reliable approach to
180 determine their concentration and thus, the extension of the reaction. Samples were periodically taken
181 from the reactor and immediately analysed. A TOC analyser (Shimadzu, mod. TOC VSCH) was used.
182 H₂O₂ concentration was determined by colorimetric titration following the titanium sulphate method
183 (Eisenberg (1943)).

184 *2.4. Biodegradability of MPs leachates*

185 The leaching of both fresh and oxidized MPs was analysed in terms of biodegradability following the
186 procedure described elsewhere (Romera-Castillo et al. (2018)). Firstly, MPs leaching experiments were
187 carried out incubating under artificial solar radiation (HQI-T Powerstar lamp, UV-A radiation by 2 Philips
188 TL100W/10 R fluorescent tubes and UV-B radiation by 2 UVA-340 fluorescent lamps) and in a water
189 bath at 28 °C, simulating the surface waters in some areas of the coastal Mediterranean Sea in summer.

190 EPS MPs in the range from 100 to 250 μm (fresh and oxidized) at a concentration of 9 g L^{-1} were added
191 to 250 mL of sterilized (autoclaved at 121 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 20 min) artificial seawater (36.9 g L^{-1} using Sea Salt
192 from Sigma-Aldrich) in quartz tubes which were incubated for 6 days of exposure time. After incubation
193 period, samples for dissolved TOC were collected after filtration through a combusted GF/F filter
194 (Whatman). Afterwards, the bioavailability of the dissolved TOC leached from plastics was evaluated.
195 An inoculum of 0.8 μm filtered surface seawater from the Blanes Bay Microbial Observatory, in the
196 coastal NW Mediterranean Sea, was added to the leaching solutions at a ratio of 9:1 (leachate: inoculum).
197 Then, NH_4Cl (10 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$) and NaH_2PO_4 (2 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$) were added to avoid microorganisms growth
198 limitation by either nitrogen or phosphorus availability. The flasks were incubated in the dark at 23 $^{\circ}\text{C}$
199 until the mixed microbial community reached the stationary phase. All the experiments were carried out
200 in triplicate. Dissolved TOC samples were collected at the beginning and at the end of the exponential
201 phase (4 days). Samples for microbial abundance were collected daily.
202 Bacterial abundance was measured by flow cytometry (BD FACSCalibur) following the method
203 described elsewhere (Gasol and Del Giorgio (2000)).

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205 **3. Results and discussion**

206 *3.1. Microplastics characterization*

207 The characterization of the MPs studied in this work is collected in **Table 1**. As can be appreciated in
208 the SEM images, also included in **Table 1** (see Figure S1 of the Supplementary Material for optical
209 microscopic images), the MPs obtained after cryogenic milling were essentially irregular and rough-shape
210 fragments. With respect to particle size, the results were consistent with the sieving, obtaining in all cases
211 a mean particle size within the corresponding sieving size-range. The elemental analysis (CHNS) and the
212 FTIR analysis (see Figures S2-S10 of the Supplementary Material for FTIR spectra) were in good
213 agreement with the corresponding polymer of the raw materials, which allowed to confirm a high degree
214 of purity of the raw plastic products. On the other hand, these results also proved that after the grinding
215 process, the polymer did not present any change in its composition with respect to the starting material.

216 The CI values calculated from FTIR spectra were very similar for PE, PVC, PP and EPS, but a
217 significantly higher value was found for PET. This is clearly due to the chemical structure of the polymers.
218 PET was the only polymer that contain carbonyl groups in its structure (*Table 1*). On the other hand, the
219 variation in the size of EPS MPs did not lead to any change in the CI estimation, so it can be confirmed
220 that the chemical structure of EPS did not change with decreasing the particle size.

Table 1. Main characteristics of the MPs studied in this work.

	Raw material	Molecular structure	SEM image	Mean particle size (μm)	Elemental analysis (CHNS) (% wt.)	CI	Water contact angle ($^\circ$)	$\text{pH}_{\text{slurry}}$
PET		157.0	C: 62.4; H: 5.1; N: <0.1; S: <0.1 O ^a : 32.5	1.31	118.5 ± 3.6	8.7		
PE		170.0	C: 84.8; H: 14.4; N: <0.1; S: <0.1 O ^a : 0.8	0.05	122.7 ± 2.8	8.7		
PVC		201.0	C: 37.5; H: 6.3; N: 0.3; S: 0.1 Cl ^a : 55.8	0.03	118.3 ± 3.7	9.1		
PP		198.0	C: 83.8; H: 14.1; N: 0.2; S: <0.1 O ^a : 1.8	0.03	124.0 ± 2.0	8.8		
EPS		27.0	C: 91.3; H: 8.0; N: 0.1; S: <0.1 O ^a : 0.6	0.09	118.3 ± 1.8	8.7		
				54.5		0.08	120.0 ± 0.5	8.9
				101.0		0.10	117.3 ± 3.5	9.0
				187.0		0.09	118.0 ± 1.3	8.9
				335.0		0.10	119.8 ± 0.8	8.8

^a Calculated by difference.^b Determined in deionized water at $\text{pH}_0 = 6$.

223 To characterize the hydrophobicity/hydrophilicity of each MP, water contact angle measurements
224 were carried out. As can be seen in **Table 1**, values within the range of 118–124° were obtained for all the
225 materials studied, clearly above 90°, typical of hydrophobic solids (Yuan and Lee (2013)). Specifically,
226 the highest water contact angle values were obtained for PE (122.7°) and PP (124.0°). The higher
227 hydrophobicity of these solids was also visually evident as they were less susceptible to being properly
228 wetted. On the other hand, it must be noted that the different EPS MP sizes did not show noticeable
229 changes in the water contact angle values, which confirms the high reproducibility of the measurement
230 technique regardless of the particle size.

231 To get further insights on the surface chemical composition of the MPs, the $\text{pH}_{\text{slurry}}$ of the MPs was
232 also determined. The results obtained operating at $\text{pH}_0 = 6$ are collected in **Table 1** (see Table S1 of the
233 Supplementary Material for complete experimental data obtained at different initial pH values). In
234 accordance with their hydrophobic nature, basic $\text{pH}_{\text{slurry}}$ values within the range of 8-9 were obtained,
235 confirming the basic character of all the MPs regardless their nature or size.

236 *3.2. Fenton oxidation of microplastics*

237 To evaluate the extension of the oxidation reaction, the MPs weight loss was measured at the end of
238 the experiments and the properties of the solids were fully characterized. As can be seen in **Figure 1a**,
239 somewhat low weight losses were found considering the relatively severe operating conditions tested.
240 Weight loss values were close to 10% regardless of the nature of the MP, which demonstrates the high
241 stability of these solids towards hydroxyl radicals attack. Considering the dose of H_2O_2 employed and the
242 loss of weight achieved, the extrapolated amount of H_2O_2 to completely remove (weight loss) a unit mass
243 of MPs was around $107 \text{ g}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}_2} \text{ g}_{\text{MP oxidized}}^{-1}$ (equivalent to $116 \text{ g}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}_2} \text{ g}_{\text{TOC mineralized}}^{-1}$). This value is
244 remarkably higher than the previously reported for the treatment of industrial wastewaters under similar
245 operating conditions (Pliego et al. (2012); Munoz et al. (2014); Munoz et al. (2016)), where values
246 between 10 and $20 \text{ g}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}_2} \text{ g}_{\text{TOC mineralized}}^{-1}$ were obtained, which further demonstrates the extremely high
247 persistence of MPs. Apart from considering the impact of the MPs nature on their overall degradation, the

248 influence of the particle size was also investigated. For such goal, EPS MPs of five different particle size
249 ranges between 20 and 500 μm were evaluated (*Figure 1b*). Although low weight losses were also found,
250 they clearly followed a trend with the MP particle size. The weight loss value achieved after the oxidation
251 process visibly increased with decreasing the MP particle size. While a weight loss value around 10%
252 was achieved in the Fenton oxidation of 250-500 μm MPs, almost 20% was reached when 20-50 μm MPs
253 were treated. Consistent with these results, the amount of H_2O_2 needed to completely remove (weight
254 loss) a unit mass of MPs was substantially decreased with decreasing the size of the MPs (values of 113,
255 107, 94, and 63 $\text{gH}_2\text{O}_2 \text{ gMP oxidized}^{-1}$, equivalent to 123, 116, 102 and 69 $\text{gH}_2\text{O}_2 \text{ gTOC mineralized}^{-1}$, were obtained
256 for the oxidation of 250-500, 150-250, 50-100 and 20-50 μm MPs, respectively). Since smaller
257 microparticles have a larger exposed surface area, these results seem to indicate that the reaction takes
258 place on the MP surface, which is attacked by hydroxyl radicals. Once the surface of the solid is
259 completely degraded, new parts of the MP are exposed, thus presumably continuing the reaction.

260 As previously indicated in the introduction, the Fenton process has been proposed in the literature as
261 a pre-treatment for the isolation of MPs in real aqueous matrices for analytical purposes since other
262 organic solids are expected to be oxidized to a higher extent given the persistence of plastics (Lares et al.
263 (2018); Tagg et al. (2016); Hurley et al. (2018)). However, although our results corroborate that subtle
264 degradation of MPs occurs regardless of their nature, they also prove that the use of the Fenton process
265 as a pre-treatment for MPs quantification may lead to an underestimation of the undersized MPs present
266 in the starting sample as they are clearly degraded to a greater extent. Accordingly, the operating
267 conditions of the Fenton process must be carefully optimized to warrant that MPs remain unchanged along
268 the oxidation treatment for MPs isolation purposes.

Figure 1. Influence of nature of MP (a) and EPS particle size (b) on the weight loss of the MPs after Fenton treatment.

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Despite the relatively low MPs weight losses achieved after Fenton oxidation, the particles suffered important changes on their surface along reaction. As representative example, **Figure 2** shows images of the EPS MPs suspensions in deionized water before and after the oxidation treatment, together with light microscopic and SEM images (light microscopic and SEM microscopic images of all of the MPs tested in this work, both fresh and oxidized, are collected in the Figures S1, S11-S13 of the Supplementary Material). As can be observed, while fresh EPS MPs float on the water matrix, a clear indication of their high hydrophobicity, the oxidised ones were distributed throughout the liquid and even settled. This visual observation suggests that after the Fenton treatment MPs become more hydrophilic, thus allowing better contact with the water phase. On the other hand, by comparing the optical microscopy images, it can be seen that oxidised MPs showed semi-transparent areas not observed in the fresh solids. This fact confirms that the reaction starts at the surface of the particles, progressively degrading them and causing a decrease in their thickness. Finally, SEM images revealed the presence of wrinkles, voids, and holes on the MP surface, which could not be observed in the fresh particles.

287 All these modifications were especially evident in PET and EPS MPs, probably due to their molecular
288 structure. The presence of aromatic rings in these MPs may increase the oxidation yield by generating
289 differences in electronic charge along the polymer structure. In fact, it is well known that hydroxyl radicals
290 preferentially attack aromatic rings and double bonds compared with alkanes (Pignatello et al. (2006)).
291 These results are in good agreement with those reported by Lang et al. (2020), who recently studied the
292 ageing of EPS MPs (~600 μm) by the Fenton process. After 7 days of reaction ($[\text{H}_2\text{O}_2]_0 = 4500 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$;
293 $[\text{Fe}^{2+}]_0 = 167.5 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$; room temperature and $\text{pH}_0 = 4$), the MPs showed a rougher surface, with small
294 cracks and holes. Furthermore, a growth in the adsorption capacity of Cd^{2+} was observed upon oxidation
295 of the MP, suggesting that surface modifications have occurred. In fact, an increase of surface oxygenated
296 groups was detected, and new absorption bands in the infrared spectrum (corresponding to the C-O, C=O,
297 and O-C=O bonds) were observed.

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299 **Figure 2.** Fresh EPS suspension (a), fresh EPS light microscopic image (b), fresh EPS SEM
300 (c), oxidized EPS suspension (d), oxidized EPS light microscopic image (e) and oxidized EPS SEM
301 image (f).

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303 To further investigate the surface changes observed in the different MPs after the Fenton process, the
304 main properties of the oxidized materials were characterized. The water angle contact, CI, $\text{pH}_{\text{slurry}}$ and
305 mean particle size of the oxidized MPs are listed in **Table 2**. Comparing the contact angle results, a clear
306 decrease in this parameter was obtained after the Fenton oxidation treatment, which corroborates the

307 increase in the hydrophilicity of the MPs. Regarding the MP nature, the variation in the water angle
308 contact value was particularly noticeable in the case of PET and EPS. In fact, the water droplet spread
309 completely on the MPs layer in these cases leading to a nearly zero apparent contact angle for PET and
310 most of EPS MP sizes. Therefore, these oxidized MPs could be classified as superhydrophilic solids, since
311 they could not be accurately measured by the optical system employed ($<5-10^\circ$) (Drelich and Chibowski
312 (2010)). Only the smallest EPS MPs tested ($<50\ \mu\text{m}$) could be measured, probably due to the smoother
313 and more homogeneous surface of the obtained MP layer compared to that of higher MP sizes, where
314 more irregularities are present favouring the fast penetration of the water droplet. In any case, the water
315 contact angle value was reduced around 70% also in this case, confirming that the oxidation process is
316 clearly increasing the hydrophilicity of the MPs (see Figure S14 of the Supplementary Material for water
317 angle contact measurements with fresh and oxidized EPS MPs ($<50\ \mu\text{m}$)). In contrast to the results
318 obtained with PET and EPS, the MPs composed by alkane polymers *i.e.* PE, PVC and PP showed slight
319 changes in their water contact angle values after oxidation ($<6\%$ reduction) (**Table 2**). Again, these results
320 can be explained by the significantly lower reactivity of alkane polymers towards hydroxyl radicals attack
321 compared to aromatic rings-bearing polymers (Lares et al. (2018)). On the other hand, the observed
322 percentage reductions in the water contact angle values for the alkane-bearing polymers were 6%, 5% and
323 $<2\%$ for PE, PP and PVC MPs, respectively, which indicates that the presence and nature of substituents
324 also affects the oxidation yield. PE does not present any substituent, which seemed to favour its
325 hydrophilization compared to the substituted alkanes. PP, which contains methyl substituents, showed a
326 slightly lower hydrophilization than PE due to the presence of such electro-neutral groups; whereas PVC,
327 which contains chlorine substituents, was the least hydrophilized MP probably due to the protection
328 offered by the halogen towards hydroxyl radical attack. In fact, it is well known that $\text{HO}\cdot$ does not readily
329 attack halogens and favours the least substituted carbons due to its electrophilic character (Pignatello et
330 al. (2006)).

Table 2. Main surface properties of oxidized MPs.

MP	Mean particle size (μm)	CI	Water contact angle ($^\circ$)	pH _{slurry}
PET	123.0	1.42	*	5.4
PE	163.0	0.10	115.5 \pm 3.2	4.5
PVC	193.0	0.04	116.3 \pm 3.3	4.2
PP	192.0	0.10	118.0 \pm 2.5	4.6
	24.1	0.24	36.0 \pm 4.8	4.7
	48.9	0.21	*	4.9
EPS	88.3	0.20	*	5.2
	169.0	0.18	*	5.1
	300.0	0.14	*	5.4

332 *Not measurable. The drop of water was quickly adsorbed by the layer of MPs, confirming its high
333 hydrophilicity.

334

335 The surface oxidation after the Fenton treatment led to a significant reduction of the pH_{slurry} from basic
336 (8-9) to slightly acidic values (4-5) for all MPs (*Table 2*). These results are consistent with the
337 aforementioned changes in the water contact angle values after treatment, since the surface hydrophilicity
338 is clearly related to the presence of oxygenated groups which acidify the solid surface (Shi et al. (2009)).
339 According to the results obtained for the oxidation of different particle sizes of EPS MPs, the pH_{slurry} of
340 the MP decreased with decreasing its particle size, which is consistent with the higher exposed surface of
341 the solid (*Table 2*). The oxidation process degrades the microparticles progressively from the surface of
342 the material, thus decreasing the particle size and increasing the exposed surface area, leading to a higher
343 degradation rate of the solids.

344 The decrease in water contact angle and pH_{slurry} indicates that oxygenated groups are incorporated on
345 the surface of the solids through the Fenton oxidation reaction (Liu et al. (2019)). Upon Fenton process,
346 different polar functional groups may be generated like hydroxyl, carbonyl, carboxyl, alcohol, ketone,

347 peroxy and ester groups, which promotes the previously observed increase in the hydrophilicity of the
348 surface. To check the possible generation of oxygenated groups, the CI was calculated from FTIR spectra
349 for each oxidized sample (**Table 2**). It must be noted that despite the subtle changes in the carbonyl peak
350 position (1850-1650 cm^{-1}), the FTIR spectra of all MPs remained practically unchanged after Fenton
351 oxidation (see Figures S2-S10 of the Supplementary Material for FTIR spectra of both fresh and oxidized
352 MPs). On the other hand, it must be noted that no significant changes were found in the elemental analyses
353 of oxidized microplastics compared with the fresh ones, and thus, it can be concluded that the chemical
354 composition of these solids remained unchanged after Fenton treatment. Comparing the CI of the oxidized
355 solids with the fresh ones, a clear increase can be seen in all MPs samples except PVC. An increase in the
356 CI is consistent with the incorporation of carboxylic groups on the surface of the solids after the oxidation
357 process. The increase of CI was higher for those MPs with aromatic groups in their chemical structure
358 (PET and EPS), while a more subtle rise in CI was found for the rest of the MPs studied (alkane-based
359 polymers). A special case is PVC, where the increase of this parameter is practically negligible. This result
360 is consistent with the lower hydrophilization observed for this plastic and again, can be related to the
361 protection offered by the chlorine substituent of the alkane chain towards hydroxyl radical attack
362 (Pignatello et al. (2006)). On the other hand, it is important to note that the MP size also showed an impact
363 on the generation of carboxyl groups. Clearly, higher CI values were obtained with decreasing the EPS
364 MP size. While the oxidation of the smallest EPS MP size ($<50 \mu\text{m}$) led to an increase of the CI from 0.09
365 to 0.24, only 0.14 was achieved with the highest EPS MP size range tested (250 – 500 μm). These results
366 corroborated that small particles with a larger exposed surface area favours the incorporation of
367 oxygenated groups and thus, the oxidation of the MP. Liu et al. (2019) obtained similar results when they
368 compared the aging of PS and PE MPs the Fenton process. After 30 days of reaction ($[\text{H}_2\text{O}_2]_0 = 4500 \text{ mg}$
369 L^{-1} ; $[\text{Fe}^{2+}]_0 = 167.5 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$; ambient temperature and $\text{pH}_0 = 4$), an increase of nearly 0.15 and 0.05 in CI
370 estimation was obtained for PS and PE, respectively.

371 The MPs hydrophilization due to the incorporation of oxygenated groups on their surface have serious
372 implications on the behaviour of the MPs. For instance, it is well-known that MPs can act as pollutant
373 carriers in the aquatic environment given their high exposed surface areas (Magni et al. (2019); Ma et al.
374 (2019); Bhat and Gogate (2021); Serrano et al. (2020)). The hydrophilization of the MPs could completely
375 change the adsorption performance of MPs. In fact, in our previous contribution (Munoz et al. (2021)),
376 where the role of MPs on the adsorption of micropollutants was investigated, we found that the Fenton
377 oxidation of MPs led to a significant decrease on their adsorption capacity of a hydrophobic
378 micropollutant, the anti-inflammatory diclofenac, while substantially increased the uptake of a
379 hydrophilic pharmaceutical, the antibiotic metronidazole.

380 Apart from considering the surface modification of the MPs upon Fenton oxidation, the impact of this
381 treatment on their size was also evaluated (**Table 2**). MPs suffered a slight decrease in their particle size
382 after reaction being this effect especially noticeable for PET (~20%) and EPS (~11%), the polymers with
383 aromatic rings in their structures. More discrete changes (~3%) were observed for the alkane polymers
384 *i.e.* PE, PVC and PP. These results are in good agreement with the main findings observed in the surface
385 modification of MPs, where clearly those polymers containing aromatic rings were more susceptible to
386 Fenton oxidation than those based on alkane chains. Surprisingly, these data differ from the obtained by
387 Liu et al. (2019), who observed a clear decrease in mean particle size in both cases, but this decrease was
388 notably larger for PE than for PS. The main reason behind this rather unexpected result can be attributed
389 to the different tensile strength of the fresh MPs tested. In the current work, expanded EPS was tested in
390 contrast to the conventional and clearly more dense PS employed in the study of Liu et al. (2019). In fact,
391 these authors mentioned that PS was more prone to chemical attack than PE, which resulted in a faster
392 oxidation of PS in the initial time. However, the higher tensile strength of the PS (56.2 MPa) employed
393 as target material compared to that of PE (27.6 MPa) led to a greater size decrease in the latter plastic. It
394 must be noted that the tensile strength of the EPS foam used as target material in this study is rather low
395 (<1 MPa) (Gnip et al. (2007); Chen et al. (2015)) and thus, it did not offer the same resistance of

396 conventional PS towards fragmentation. On the other hand, the initial size of the MP tested did not show
397 a relevant impact on the particle reduction yield, which indicates that this phenomenon is obviously much
398 slower than the hydrophilization of the MPs surface.

399 To get deeper insights onto the reduction of MPs particle size along Fenton oxidation, particle size
400 distributions were also analysed. As representative example, **Figure 3** shows the particle size distribution
401 of EPS MPs (150-250 μm) before and after Fenton oxidation (see Figures S15-S23 of the Supplementary
402 Material for the experimental data obtained with all the MPs tested). Clearly, oxidized MPs showed a
403 lower proportion of large particles ($>200 \mu\text{m}$) than the fresh MPs, while the opposite trend was observed
404 for the smaller particles ($<200 \mu\text{m}$). These results are consistent with the above-mentioned hypothesis,
405 evidencing that MPs are progressively breaking down along the oxidation process. The effect of the
406 oxidation by Fenton process, and other related AOPs, on the size of MPs has been scarcely investigated
407 in the literature, probably due to the high persistency of these solids (Jiang et al. (2021); Liu et al. (2019)).
408 Evidently, size reduction is only observed when the oxidation of MPs is remarkably high, *i.e.* their surface
409 has been strongly oxidized and oxygen functional groups are largely introduced. All in all, these results
410 are in agreement with the work of Liu et al. (2019), where a progressive increase in the proportion of
411 smaller microparticles of PE and PS throughout the Fenton oxidation was found while studying the aging
412 behaviour of MPs.

413 Although all the experiments performed were carried out using deionized water as reaction matrix, no
414 significant changes are expected neither in the extension nor in the rate of the process if waters with a low
415 content of organic matter and/or inorganic ions would be treated considering the relatively severe
416 operating conditions in terms of temperature (80 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) but also in terms of H_2O_2 dose (10 g L^{-1}) employed
417 in this work.

Figure 3. Particle size distribution of EPS 150-250 μm.

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421 3.3. Fenton oxidation of nanoplastics

422 In the previous section, it was demonstrated that the oxidation of MPs is started on the surface of the
 423 solids leading to the formation of oxygen functional groups, which consequently increase their acidity
 424 and hydrophilicity and progressively reduce their size, ultimately resulting in subtle weight losses.
 425 Assuming that MPs would continue their size reduction along Fenton oxidation and to get deeper insights
 426 onto the extension of the oxidation process and thus the mineralization yield, a new experiment was
 427 carried out using commercial PS NPs (140 nm). As these particles were homogeneously dispersed in
 428 water and did not settle, the evolution of their concentration was followed by analysing the TOC along
 429 reaction. Evidently, not only the solid particles but also possible organic leachates released from the NPs
 430 to the liquid phase would be considered, that is why the evolution of the reaction was also followed by
 431 periodically analysing the solid particles by TEM microscopy.

432 **Figure 4** collects the TEM images of the solid particles at each reaction stage together with the
 433 evolution of TOC along Fenton oxidation of PS NPs. As can be seen, fresh PS NPs were smooth spheres
 434 with a completely homogeneous particle size. Along Fenton oxidation, they suffered important changes
 435 and particle breakdown, leading in the end to an undefined agglomerated solid composed by NPs

436 fragments. Consistent with these observations, TOC concentration was progressively decreased along
437 reaction, reaching up to 70% mineralization after applying 15 doses of H₂O₂. Considering the dose of
438 H₂O₂ employed and the degree of mineralization achieved, the amount of H₂O₂ needed to completely
439 mineralize a unit mass of NPs was 21.5 gH₂O₂ gNP(TOC) mineralized⁻¹. This value is quite close to those
440 previously reported in the literature for the treatment of real wastewaters (Pliego et al. (2012); Munoz et
441 al. (2014); Munoz et al. (2016)). For instance, in our previous contributions (Munoz et al. (2014); Munoz
442 et al. (2016)), values of 12.1 and 14.3 gH₂O₂ gTOC mineralized⁻¹ were required in the treatment of sawmill and
443 hospital wastewaters, respectively. These results clearly demonstrate that hydroxyl radical attack can
444 completely mineralize the plastic particles and opens the door for the intensification of the process so it
445 could be applied for water treatment purposes, which was out of the scope of the current study.

446
447
448

Figure 4. Degradation of PS NPs along the oxidation reaction. TEM images (a), TOC (b).

449 Since the release of organic leachates along the oxidation of MPs/NPs is expected, an additional
450 experiment focused on the degradation of a dissolved plasticiser was also carried out to determine if the
451 presence of dissolved species in the water phase can substantially affect the kinetics and extension of
452 MPs/NPs oxidation, or if these compounds would even remain in the liquid phase once the solid particles
453 are removed. For such goal, diethyl phthalate (DEP), one of the most frequently used plasticisers in
454 numerous plastic materials was selected (Cao et al. (2022)). This experiment was performed under similar
455 operating conditions to those previously used for the oxidation of MPs and NPs (the main properties of
456 the phthalate and the oxidation stoichiometry are provided in Table S2 of the Supplementary Material).
457 Notably, the complete degradation of DEP was achieved after 2 h reaction time using the stoichiometric
458 H₂O₂ dose for its complete degradation (H₂O₂ and Fe³⁺ were added only at the beginning of the reaction,
459 see Figure S24 of the Supplementary Material for experimental results). These results highlight the high
460 degradation rate of these compounds compared to the degradation of MPs and NPs. Therefore, it can be
461 concluded that the possible leachates produced during the process will be also degraded in the course of
462 the reaction.

463 The obtained results imply that, on the one hand, the size of the solid is a critical factor when using
464 this technology for the oxidation of MPs and NPs. Clearly, NPs are more prone to be oxidized by Fenton
465 oxidation given their higher exposed surface. On the other hand, it is demonstrated that plastic residues
466 can be finally mineralised, including the possible leachates released from the solids.

467 *3.4. Biodegradability of oxidized MPs leachates*

468 It is well-known that along AOP treatments, the intermediates generated can show even more harmful
469 than the target compounds (da Silva et al. (2014); Munoz et al. (2011); de Luna et al. (2014)) and thus,
470 the study of the biodegradability of the leachates released from the solids to the aqueous phase offers a
471 deeper understanding of the Fenton oxidation of MPs/NPs and its potential environmental implications.
472 Once demonstrated that MPs underwent a surface chemical oxidation that ultimately resulted in high
473 mineralization yields, the possible leaching of MPs upon Fenton reaction was analysed in terms of

474 biodegradability following the procedure described elsewhere (Romera-Castillo et al., 2018). For this
475 study, EPS MPs (100 - 250 μm) were selected. After six days of incubation (photodegradation in aqueous
476 saline media), simulating the surface seawaters, fresh and oxidized EPS microplastics leached 104 and
477 205 μM of dissolved TOC, respectively. Bacterial incubation assays were carried out afterwards using
478 those leaching solutions. Remarkably, 24 and 63 μM of dissolved TOC were consumed in the fresh and
479 oxidized EPS microplastics, respectively, which are in the same range than other commercial plastics
480 under similar conditions (Romera-Castillo et al., 2022). In fact, bacterial abundance was higher in the
481 solution coming from the oxidized EPS sample compared to the fresh one, resulting in $5.4 \cdot 10^{-6}$ and $3.5 \cdot 10^{-6}$
482 cell mL^{-1} at the end of the biodegradation experiments, respectively. Therefore, it was confirmed that
483 the leachates from oxidized EPS MPs did not inhibit bacterial growth, and in fact, they were even more
484 biodegradable than the leachates released from the fresh solids since 30% and 23% of the dissolved TOC
485 was consumed, respectively.

486 **4. Conclusions**

487 The results obtained in this work have demonstrated that MPs undergo important changes along
488 intensified Fenton treatment. The oxidation process starts in the particle surface, leading to its
489 physical/morphological modification (creation of wrinkles, voids, and holes) and also chemical alteration
490 due the formation of oxygen functional groups, which consequently increase its hydrophilicity and surface
491 acidity. Furthermore, MPs progressively reduce their size, which ultimately results in their complete
492 oxidation to CO_2 . The nature of the plastic particles has a relevant impact on its overall oxidation, being
493 more prone to be oxidized those polymers which contain aromatic rings in their structures (EPS and PET)
494 compared to those formed by aliphatic chains (PE, PP and PVC). In the latter, the presence of substituents
495 as chlorine increases their resistance to be oxidized. Clearly, the decrease of MPs particle size increases
496 their reactivity achieving high oxidation yields due to the higher exposed surface area readily available to
497 be attacked by hydroxyl radicals. Along the oxidation process, which occurs from the surface to the core
498 of plastic particles, the release of leachates is assumed. Nevertheless, these dissolved species are

499 remarkably more quickly oxidized than the solid particles. Notably, dissolved oxidation intermediates do
500 not inhibit bacterial growth, and in fact, they can be even more biodegradable than the leachates released
501 from the fresh solids. All this knowledge is crucial for the understanding of the fate of MPs along Fenton
502 oxidation and opens the door for the design and optimization of this process for water treatment.
503 Furthermore, it offers relevant information that must be considered when the application of Fenton is
504 intended for MPs analytical purposes as the oxidation can significantly modify the solid particles and even
505 remove those of smaller ranges, leading to an underestimation in the quantification of MPs.

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515 **Conflicts of interest**

516 There are no conflicts to declare.

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